

Stress and Coping Strategies of PE Teachers

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15545696

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Abstract:

This study was conducted to shed light on the contrasting reality, indicating stress and coping of PE teachers in various settings, specifically at the school level. In this context, the study aimed to determine the level of stress, coping strategies, and performance of PE teachers in a medium-sized School Division in the Northern part of Negros Occidental for School Year 2022 – 2023. The data needed for this descriptive research was collected from 123 Physical Education teachers using a self-made instrument that passed the stringent tests of validity and reliability. The ensuing analysis showed that PE teachers experience a moderate level of stress in terms of organizational factors, personal factors and environmental factors but demonstrate a high level of coping utilizing appraisal focused strategies, problem focused strategies and emotional focused strategies. The results of this study revealed that Physical Education teachers experience stress in the work environment which should be given attention to this could affect performance and efficiency of an individual. The coping strategies employed by the teachers could also be studied as a basis for developments.

Keywords: Physical Education, Stress and Coping Strategies, PE Teachers

Introduction:

Nature of the Problem

Every individual has his way of dealing with stress. Still, there are some simple yet powerful proven coping techniques – and by understanding their pros and cons, an individual will be able to choose the strategy that is right for an individual. How an individual manages stress must work for him, so that he can develop a realistic, practical plan that fits his own needs (Horowitz and McIntosh, 2018).

The ability of teachers to cope with stress and challenges significantly impacts their performance in the classroom. Effective coping mechanisms allow teachers to manage the demands of their jobs, leading to better emotional regulation, increased resilience, and improved decision-making. Teachers who cope well are more likely to build positive relationships with students, create a supportive learning environment, and experience greater job satisfaction. Ultimately, a teacher's ability to cope with stress is essential for their well-being and the success of their students.

Physical Education teachers often encounter various stressors that can negatively impact their work performance. This study aims to explore the role of coping strategies in mitigating these stressors' effects. By examining the relationship between stress factors, coping mechanisms, and job performance, we can identify effective strategies for enhancing teacher well-being and productivity.

Current State of Knowledge

The stress of PE Teachers. Ciaramicoli (2016) provides practical steps for Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT), such as identifying triggers like anger, sadness, stress, and anxiety; recording the thoughts or beliefs that arise from these triggers; and documenting the consequences of these triggers and the associated thoughts. The author also emphasized the importance of maintaining authenticity and integrity, suggesting that attempting to please others to stabilize a fragile sense of self can lead to inauthenticity and heightened stress.

Furthermore, Richard Rohr, as cited by Ciaramicoli (2016), posits that individuals cannot heal what they do not acknowledge; unrecognized stress remains in control, causing emotional harm. Extreme stress can have severe emotional tolls, with minor episodes being manageable through natural defense mechanisms. However, chronic stress, which persists over long periods, can be physically and psychologically debilitating (American Psychological Association Journal, 2017).

Coping with stress is a dynamic process, and individuals may find that different situations necessitate different coping strategies (Kelburn & Whitlock, 2020). According to Carver and Smith, as quoted by Horowitz and

McIntosh (2018), coping efforts aim to prevent or diminish threat, harm, and loss or to reduce associated distress. The authors further asserted that coping is a broad concept encompassing all thoughts and actions used to make a threatening situation more manageable. Furthermore, Horowitz and McIntosh (2018) noted that psychologists debate the efficacy of emotion-focused coping, acknowledging that while it may be suitable in the short term, it requires strategies that actively address one's feelings rather than avoiding them.

Teaching involves both high pressure and serious responsibilities, factors that are often beyond the control of the individual. Hence, it is imperative to understand how teachers become more effective at dealing with the everyday demands and challenges associated with the teaching profession to help students reach their full potential. Not only will this benefit the teachers by protecting themselves from stress, but also promote their engagement, learning, and mastery of skills (Sorenson, 2017).

There are so many different ways of adapting to situations. Coping is the conscious and unconscious efforts we put into solving problems and reducing stress. It is the mind's built-in troubleshooting program that aims to restore its optimum functioning state. In psychology, coping skills or coping strategies are a set of adaptive tools that we proactively administer to avoid burnout. These tools can be our thoughts, emotions, and actions and are dependent on our personality patterns (Chowdhury, 2019).

Theoretical Underpinnings

This research study was anchored on a model of stress by Cooper and Payne (1978), as cited by Judge and Robins (2011), that presents the potential sources of stress and categorizes it into three potential stressors: environmental, organizational, and personal. For each category of the potential stressors, it identifies sources of stress. It reveals the experienced stress as influenced by individual differences. It shows the physiological, psychological, and behavioral symptoms as the consequences of stress.

The theory of goodness of fit, as suggested by Folkman and her partners in the field of coping, is relevant to this (Folkman et al., 1979; Roussi et al., 2000). According to this theory, the functionality / effectiveness of a strategy depends on how well-matched the coping strategy is with the characteristics of the stress-inducing stimulus (especially regarding its controllability). So, a problem-focused strategy is functionally adaptive when adopted in order to deal with a stressful stimulus that is perceived to be controllable. In such a case, an emotion-focused strategy would impede adaptability. On the other hand, an emotion-focused strategy is functional/adaptive when the event/stimulus is considered impossible to control/modify. In such a case, every problem-focused coping effort should be considered adaptability impeding. This theory is only partially borne out in practice, perhaps because of conceptual problems and methodological inadequacies (Masel et al., 1996).

Moreover, this study is also anchored on the theory of performance (TOP) of Elger (2013), which develops and relates foundational concepts to form a framework that can be used to explain performance and performance improvements. It was theorized that to perform, it is important to produce valued results. This theory covers the axioms that were proposed for effective performance improvements. These involve a performer's mindset, immersion in an enriching environment, and engagement in reflective practice (Delfinado, 2013).

Objectives of the Study

This study was conducted to determine the level of stress and coping of Physical Education Teachers in one district of Negros Occidental. Specifically, it sought to determine: 1) the level of stress according to the areas of Organizational Factors, Personal Factors and Environmental Factors and the level of coping strategies employed in the areas of Appraisal-Focused Strategies, Problem-Focused Strategies and Emotion-Focused Strategies; 2) the significant difference, if any, in the level of stress and coping based on demographic groupings and 3) Is there a significant relationship between the level of stress and the level of coping of PE teachers.

Methodology:

This section, the researcher presents the research design. The locale of the study, subject and respondents of the study, data gathering instrument, validity, and reliability of the research instrument, data gathering procedure, analytical schemes, and statistical tools.

Research Design

This study used a descriptive research design to determine the stress and coping of PE teachers. According to McCombes (2019), descriptive research involves the description, recording, analysis, and interpretation of the present nature, composition, or processes of phenomena that focus on prevailing conditions or how a person aims to describe a population, situation, or phenomenon accurately and systematically.

Respondents

The study utilized the total population of PE teachers which were the one hundred twenty-three (123) Elementary Physical Education teachers in District I in the medium Division of the northern part of Negros Occidental. Since the total number of respondents was manageable, a random sampling technique was not employed.

Instrument

The survey questionnaire covered 42 items to determine the level of stress of Physical Education teachers based on organizational, personal factors and environmental factors as well as coping strategies in terms of Appraisal-Focused Strategies, Problem-Focused Strategies and Emotion-Focused Strategies. Responses to each item were based on the following scaling: (5) with a verbal interpretation of Very High extent, (4) for High level, (3) for Moderate level, (2) for Low level, and (1) for Very Low level. The scale ensures quantitative data to be used to analyze and interpret the participants' sentiments systematically.

Procedures for Data Collection

After validity and reliability of the instrument was established, a formal request was sent to the District Superintendent for approval to conduct the study. After the request was approved it was distributed to the School Heads where it was then administered to the respondents and collected after one week.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objective 1 used the descriptive-analytical scheme and mean as statistical tool to determine the level of stress of PE teachers according to the areas of Organizational Factors, Personal Factors and Emotional Factors.

Objective 2 also used the descriptive-analytical scheme and mean as statistical tool to determine the level of coping strategies employed by PE teachers. For Objective 3 relational-analytical scheme was and Spearman – Rho as statistical tool was used to determine the significant relationship between the levels of stress and coping strategies of PE teachers.

Ethical Considerations

The study adhered to strict ethical guidelines by guaranteeing voluntary participation, informed consent, and data confidentiality; respondents participated freely, understood the study's purpose, and were assured their identities would remain anonymous, ensuring compliance with established principles regarding voluntary participation, informed consent, risk of harm, confidentiality, and anonymity.

Results and Discussions:

This section presents an overview of the study's discoveries based on the data gathered, tallied, and tabulated to facilitate the statistical analysis and interpretation following the objectives. Following this, the researcher goes into detail about the study results, which are presented below.

Level of Stress of PE Teachers in the Areas of Organizational Factors, Personal Factors, and Environment Factors

Table 1

Level of Stress of PE Teachers in the Areas of Organizational Factors

Organizational factors Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a PE teacher, I have. .</i>		
1. too much workload assigned by the school head.	3.30	Moderate Level
2. limited utilization of break time due to workload.	3.49	Moderate Level
3. not openly express concerns, ideas, and thoughts with others.	3.08	Moderate Level
4. limitation on promotion opportunities.	3.07	Moderate Level
5. job assignments and organizational structure are not defined clearly.	3.09	Moderate Level
6. disagreement/misunderstanding with subordinates and colleagues.	2.54	Moderate Level
7. difficulty in establishing rapport with colleagues and school heads.	2.46	Low Level
Overall Mean	3.00	Moderate Level

Table 1 shows that the level of stress of PE teachers in the area of Organizational Factors is moderate, with a mean of 3.00. On the other hand, item 7, which states, "difficulty in establishing rapport with colleagues and school heads," has the lowest mean of 2.46, interpreted as "low level." The respondents obtained the highest mean of 3.49, interpreted as "moderate level" in item 2, which states, "limited utilization of break time due to workload."

The data indicate that physical education teachers experience a moderate level of stress related to organizational factors. Notably, difficulty in establishing rapport with colleagues and school heads emerges as a significant concern, reflecting a lower stress level that may still impact collaboration and support. In contrast, the highest stress is associated with the limited use of break time due to workload, underscoring how heavy workloads can

exacerbate stress. This implies that improving interpersonal relationships and managing workloads effectively are essential for enhancing the overall well-being of PE teachers. Addressing these areas may lead to a more supportive work environment and better stress management among educators.

The job stress of physical education (PE) teachers is significantly higher than that of other professional groups. Research by Abbasnejad, Farahani, and Nakhaei (2013) reveals a significant inverse relationship between time management and job stress. Additionally, Hosseini, Nourbakhsh, and Sepasi (2023) recommend that organizational managers consider these factors and offer employees opportunities to improve their time management skills, which may help reduce stress levels.

Table 2
Level of Stress of PE Teachers in the Areas of Personal Factors

Personal factors		
Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a PE teacher, I experienced. .</i>		
1. insufficient take-home pay.	3.90	High Level
2. serious illness in the family.	2.88	Moderate Level
3. difficulty in maintaining family expenditures.	3.30	Moderate Level
4. conflict with a colleague.	2.26	Low Level
5. unsettled family concerns.	2.15	Low
6. caring for dependents like children or elderly relatives.	2.72	Moderate Level
7. a feeling of burnout.	3.14	Moderate Level
Overall Mean	2.91	Moderate Level

Table 2 depicts that the level of stress of PE teachers in the area of personal factors is moderate, with an overall mean of 2.91. Item 5, stating "unsettled family concerns." yielded the lowest mean of 2.15, interpreted as "low level," respectively. Contrastingly, Item 1, which states "insufficient take-home pay." yielded the highest mean of 3.90, interpreted as a "high level."

These findings indicate that physical education teachers experience a moderate level of stress related to personal factors. Among these, unsettled family concerns represent a lower stress level, implying that while this issue is present, it may not significantly impact teachers' overall stress. In contrast, insufficient take-home pay emerges as a prominent source of stress, highlighting financial concerns as a critical challenge for educators. These results indicate that addressing financial compensation may be essential for reducing stress among PE teachers and improving their overall well-being.

Schaack et al. (2021) found that teachers who left their positions often felt they lacked essential job resources. This observation underscores important mechanisms through which higher salaries could strengthen the teaching workforce. Furthermore, García and Han (2022) highlight that changes in teacher salaries may also play a critical role in addressing persistent achievement gaps, as salary adjustments can influence overall teaching quality.

The research conducted by Rosete et al. (2022) indicates that while the College of Teacher Education has some sports facilities and equipment, specific sports such as aquatics, athletics, baseball, and basketball are insufficiently equipped. This finding underscores the need for school administrators, particularly in the Physical Education department, to regularly assess the availability of necessary facilities and equipment. Additionally, Roccliffe et al. (2023) highlight that one-third of countries perceive the provision of sports equipment as below average, with 83% of schools lacking athletics track and over half without an outdoor all-weather surface. Furthermore, more than a quarter of schools do not have access to a grass pitch, revealing significant gaps in sports resources that must be addressed.

Table 3
Level of Stress of PE Teachers in the Areas of Environmental Factors

Environmental factors		
Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a PE teacher, I observed. .</i>		
1. inadequate PE equipment and facilities.	3.95	High Level
2. insufficient budget allocation for PE supplies.	3.94	High Level
3. Insufficient budget allocation for Sports equipment and facilities maintenance.	3.91	High Level
4. lack of administration support.	3.07	Moderate Level
5. Some teachers do not cooperate in PE activities and programs.	2.93	Moderate Level
6. Absence of Internet connection and learning resources.	3.44	Moderate Level
7. lack of parental support of learners in PE activities.	3.24	Moderate Level
Overall Mean	3.50	High Level

The level of stress of PE Teachers in the area of environmental factors is shown in Table 3. It can be observed that the overall mean of this area is 3.50, interpreted as "high level." Specifically, item 5, which states, "Some teachers not cooperating in PE activities and programs." obtained the lowest mean of 2.93, interpreted as

"moderate level." while item 1, which states "inadequate PE equipment and facilities." obtained the highest mean of 3.95, interpreted as "high level."

In view of the findings of this study, it can be implied that the stress levels of physical education (PE) teachers in relation to environmental factors indicate a generally high level of stress within this area. Notably, the item concerning the lack of cooperation from some teachers in PE activities and programs reflects moderate stress, indicating that this issue may not be as impactful as others. In contrast, the item addressing inadequate PE equipment and facilities reveals a significantly higher stress level, highlighting a critical area that requires immediate attention. These insights underscore the need for targeted interventions to address environmental factors affecting PE teachers and to improve their overall working conditions.

Level of Coping Strategies of PE Teachers in the Areas of Appraisal-Focused Strategies, Problem-Focused Strategies and Emotion-Focused Strategies

Table 4
Level of Coping Strategies of PE Teachers in the Area of Appraisal-focused Strategies

Appraisal-focused Strategies		
Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a PE teacher, I . .</i>		
1. usually face the problem with a positive attitude.	4.08	High Level
2. usually change my way of thinking to solve the problem.	4.02	High Level
3. take a short vacation or break to temporarily divert my attention.	3.45	Moderate Level
4. entertain thoughts of taking a break.	3.76	High Level
5. keep my emotions when my superior/subordinate annoys me.	3.60	High Level
6. distance me from the problem or challenge.	3.45	Moderate Level
7. make instant decisions when I feel pressured at work.	3.20	Moderate Level
Overall Mean	3.65	High Level

Table 4 reveals that the level of coping strategies of PE Teachers in the area of appraisal-focused is high, with an overall mean of 3.65. A "high level" of coping strategy was shown in item 4.08, which states, "usually face the problem with a positive attitude," with a mean of 4.08. In contrast, item 7, which states, "make instant decisions when I feel pressured at work," has the lowest mean of 3.20, interpreted as a "moderate level." The findings indicate that PE teachers struggle with instant decision-making under pressure despite generally maintaining a positive attitude. For instance, during an intense game, a teacher may find it challenging to quickly decide whether to substitute a player or change strategies. In contrast, some educators believe that focusing on personal appraisal strategies, like mindfulness and scenario training, could improve their decision-making skills in high-pressure situations. By practicing these strategies, teachers can enhance their ability to remain calm and responsive during critical moments, effectively balancing a positive mindset with the quick thinking required in intense scenarios.

Baraquia (2022) explores the various coping strategies employed by teachers to overcome challenges in their profession, highlighting both constructive and non-constructive coping mechanisms. Furthermore, Culajara (2024) investigates the strategies and challenges faced by physical education teachers in delivering instruction post-pandemic, emphasizing the importance of technology-based instructions and socio-emotional preparedness.

Table 5
Level of Coping Strategies of PE Teachers in the Area of Problem-focused Strategies

Problem-focused Strategies		
Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a PE teacher, I . .</i>		
1. attend a seminar to enhance our skills and acquire knowledge.	3.57	High Level
2. perform analysis of courses of action in providing solutions to the problem.	3.54	High Level
3. create strategies to handle problems.	3.74	High Level
4. solve the problem/conflict in a win-win solution.	3.83	High Level
5. provide solutions rather than avoiding problems.	3.97	High Level
6. use assessment strategies to identify problems.	3.80	High Level
7. handle problems in a calm and focus to come up with a positive solution.	3.93	High Level
Overall Mean	3.77	High Level

As reflected in Table 5, the level of coping strategies of PE teachers in the area of problem-focused strategies is high, with an overall mean of 3.77. The respondents obtained the highest mean score of 3.97, interpreted as "high level" in item 5, which states, "provide solutions rather than avoiding problems," however, item 2, which states, "perform analysis of courses of action in providing solutions to the problem" obtained the lowest mean of 3.54, interpreted as "high level."

This implies that PE teachers effectively use problem-focused coping strategies, especially in providing solutions rather than avoiding issues. For instance, when encountering a scheduling conflict for a sports event, a teacher might proactively engage with stakeholders to find a resolution. Conversely, some educators suggest that while they are skilled at generating solutions, they may struggle with analyzing the best courses of action. This underscores the need for targeted strategies, such as decision-making workshops, to enhance their analytical abilities.

The proposed solutions to the problem involve adaptations that enable educators to implement an integrated special pedagogical approach to addressing impairments (Apelmo, 2021). It is essential for teachers to empower themselves to navigate their unique realities effectively (Gonçalves et al., 2020). This empowerment is crucial for fostering resilience and enhancing their teaching practices in challenging environments.

Table 6
Level of Coping Strategies of PE Teachers in the Area of Emotional-focused Strategies

Emotional-focused Strategies Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a PE teacher, I . .</i>		
1. confide emotions to colleagues and the school head.	3.41	Moderate Level
2. take a coffee break and have a light conversation.	3.60	High Level
3. take time to walk and hang out with friends.	3.64	High Level
4. connect with friends on social media.	3.79	High Level
5. express emotion calmly and constructively.	3.88	High Level
6. suppress emotion to one's self in order not to avoid burden on others.	3.46	Moderate Level
7. Spend leisure time with colleagues/family.	3.83	High Level
Overall Mean	3.66	High Level

The data presented in Table 6 depicts the level of coping strategies of PE Teachers in the area of emotional-focused strategies, which has an overall mean of 3.66, interpreted as "high level." Notably, item 5, which states, "express emotion calmly and constructively," has the highest mean of 3.88, interpreted as "high level," however, item 1, which states, "confides emotions to colleagues and the school head," has the lowest mean of 3.41, interpreted as "moderate level."

The data shows that PE teachers effectively use emotional-focused coping strategies, particularly in expressing emotions calmly and constructively. For example, during stressful situations, a teacher might manage their feelings by communicating effectively with students and maintaining a positive environment. In contrast, some educators find it challenging to confide their emotions to colleagues or school leaders, indicating a need for improvement in this area. This highlights the importance of fostering a supportive environment where teachers feel comfortable sharing their feelings, as this could enhance their emotional resilience and overall well-being. Sezer and Uzun (2020) found that when school principals are good at leading social and emotional learning, teachers trust the school more and do a better job. This suggests that a principal's leadership style can significantly impact both teacher trust and performance.

Additionally, research by Gimbert et al. (2023) shows that understanding emotions, goals, and values is crucial. It's about recognizing the link between what a person thinks, feels, and does.

Table 7
Differences in the Level of Stress of PE Teachers in the Area of Organizational Factors When Grouped and Compared According to Demographic

Variables	Categories	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U - test	Sig. Level	p-value	Interpretation
Age	Younger	63	66.54	1604.0	0.147	0.147	Not Significant
	Older	60	57.23				
Civil Status	Single	38	70.54	1290.5	0.075	0.075	Not Significant
	Married	85	58.18				
Length of Service	Shorter	65	64.04	1752.0	0.05	0.501	Not Significant
	Longer	58	59.72				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	88	61.61	1505.5	0.846	0.846	Not Significant
	Higher	35	62.99				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	60	65.61	1676.5	0.272	0.272	Not Significant
	Higher	63	58.56				

Table 7 presents the difference in PE teachers' stress levels in the area of organizational factors when grouped and compared according to variables. In terms of age, the computed U was 1604.00 with a p-value of 0.075, which is greater than 0.05 level of significance, interpreted as "not significant." Consequently, the hypothesis, which states "there is no significant difference in the level of stress of PE teachers in the area of organizational factors when grouped and compared according to age, was accepted. On the other hand, when grouped and compared according to civil status, there exists no significant difference in the level of stress of PE teachers in the area of organizational factors with the computed U of 1290.50 and the p-value of 0.075, which is greater than 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the hypothesis, which states "there is no significant difference in the level of stress of PE teachers in the area of organizational factors when grouped and compared according to civil status, was accepted. Further analysis of the data shows that when grouped and compared according to length of service, the computed U test was 1752.0 with a p-value of 0.0501, which is greater than 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the hypothesis, which states "there is no significant difference in the level of stress of PE teachers in the area of organizational factors when grouped and compared according to length of service, was accepted.

Furthermore, in terms of highest educational attainment, the result shows that there exists no significant difference with the computed U test of 1505.5 and p-value of 0.846, which is greater than the level of significance of 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis, which states "there is no significant difference in the level of stress of PE teachers in the area of organizational factors when grouped and compared according to highest educational attainment, was accepted. Moreover, in terms of average family monthly income, the result shows that there exists no significant difference with the computed U test of 1676.5 and p-value of 0.272, which is greater than the level of significance of 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis, which states "there is no significant difference on the level of stress of PE teachers in the area of organizational factors when grouped and compared according to average family monthly income, was accepted.

The research findings implied that the level of stress experienced by PE teachers in relation to organizational factors is not significantly influenced by their age, civil status, length of service, educational attainment, or family income. This implies that other factors, such as workload, administrative tasks, and school climate, may play a more significant role in determining teacher stress levels. Further research could explore these factors in more detail to develop effective strategies for reducing teacher stress and improving job satisfaction.

Table 8
Differences in the Level of Stress of PE Teachers in the Area of Personal Factors When Grouped and Compared According to Demographics.

Variables	Categories	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U - test	Sig. Level	p-value	Interpretation
Age	Younger	63	68.56	1477.0		0.036	Significant
	Older	60	55.12				
Civil Status	Single	38	59.82	1532.0		0.649	Not Significant
	Married	85	62.98				
Length of Service	Shorter	65	66.18	1614.0	0.05	0.168	Not Significant
	Longer	58	57.32				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	88	61.46	1492.0		0.790	Not Significant
	Higher	35	63.36				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	60	70.19	1398.0		0.013	Significant
	Higher	63	54.20				

The data in Table 8 depicts the difference in the level of stress of PE Teachers in the area of personal factors when grouped and compared according to variables. Specifically, in the variable age, when the data of the younger and the older groups are compared and tested, the computed U test was 1477.0 with a p-value of 0.036, which is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. This indicates that there exists a significant difference in the level of stress of PE teachers in the area of personal factors when grouped and compared according to age. Hence, the null hypothesis, which states "there is no significant difference on the level of stress of PE Teachers in the area of personal factors when grouped and compared according to age," is rejected. In terms of civil status, the computed U was 1532.0 with a p-value of 0.649, which is greater than the 0.05 level of significance and is interpreted as "not significant." Therefore, the hypothesis, "there is no significant difference in the level of stress of PE Teachers in the area of personal factors when grouped and compared according to civil status," was accepted. When grouped and compared according to the length of service, there exists no significant difference in the level of stress of PE Teachers in the area of personal factors when grouped and compared according to the length of service with the computed U of 1614.0 and p-value of 0.168, which is greater than the level of significance of 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis, which states that "there is no significant difference in the level of stress of PE teachers in the area of personal factors when grouped and compared according to length

of service," was accepted. Moreover, there exists no significant difference in the level of stress of PE Teachers in the area of personal factors when grouped and compared according to highest educational attainment with the computed U of 1492.0 and p-value of 0.790, which is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Consequently, the hypothesis, which states, "there is no significant difference in the level of stress of PE Teachers in the area of personal factors when grouped and compared according to highest educational attainment," was accepted. Lastly, when grouped and compared according to average family monthly income, there exists significant difference in the level of stress of PE Teachers in the area of personal factors when grouped and compared according to average monthly income with the computed U of 1398.0 and p-value of 0.013 which is less than the level of significance of 0.05.

Further analysis, however, reveals that the level of stress experienced by PE teachers in relation to personal factors is not significantly influenced by their civil status, length of service, or educational attainment. However, age and family income appear to be a significant factor, with lower-income teachers experiencing higher levels of stress. This implies that socio-economic factors play a crucial role in teacher well-being. Further research could explore the specific stressors associated with lower income and investigate potential interventions to mitigate these stressors and improve the overall well-being of PE teachers.

Table 9

Differences in the Level of Stress of PE Teachers in the Area of Environmental Factors When Grouped and Compared According to Variables

Variables	Categories	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U - test	Sig. Level	P-value	Interpretation
Age	Younger	63	63.73	1781.0	0.580	0.580	Not Significant
	Older	60	60.18				
Civil Status	Single	38	59.59	1523.5	0.615	0.615	Not Significant
	Married	85	63.08				
Length of Service	Shorter	65	63.38	1795.0	0.05	0.649	Not Significant
	Longer	58	60.46				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	88	62.73	1476.0	0.719	0.719	Not Significant
	Higher	35	60.17				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	60	67.58	1555.0	0.089	0.089	Not Significant
	Higher	63	56.68				

Table 9 illustrates the difference in the level of stress of PE Teachers in the area of environmental factors when grouped and compared according to variables. Results show that when grouped and compared according to age, the computed U was 1781.0 with a p-value of 0.580, which is greater than the 0.05 level of significance, interpreted as "not significant." As a result, the null hypothesis, "there is no significant difference in the level of stress of PE teachers in the area of environmental factors when grouped and compared according to age," was accepted. Results further show that in terms of civil status, there exists no significant difference in the level of stress of PE Teachers in the area of environmental factors when grouped and compared. This was evident on the computed U test of 1523.5 with the p-value of 0.615, which is greater than the level of significance of 0.05. Therefore, the hypothesis, which states, "there is no significant difference in the level of stress of PE Teachers in the area of environmental factors when grouped and compared according to civil status," was accepted. Moreover, when grouped and compared according to the length of service, the computed U test of 1795.0 with a p-value of 0.649, which is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. This signifies that there is no significant difference in the level of stress of PE Teachers in the area of environmental factors. Hence, the hypothesis, which states, "there is no significant difference in the level of stress of PE Teachers in the area of environmental factors when grouped and compared according to the length of service," was accepted. On the other hand, when grouped and compared according to highest educational attainment, there exists no significant difference with the computed U of 1476.0 and the p-value of 0.719, which is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the hypothesis, which states, "there is no significant difference in the level of stress of PE Teachers in the area of environmental factors when grouped and compared according to highest educational attainment," was accepted. Lastly, when grouped and compared according to average family monthly income, there was no significant difference in the level of stress of PE Teachers in the area of personal factors when grouped and compared according to average monthly income with the computed U of 1555.0 and p-value of 0.089, which is greater than the significance level of 0.05.

Considering these findings, the level of stress experienced by PE teachers in relation to environmental factors is not significantly influenced by their age, civil status, length of service, educational attainment, or family income. This implies that other factors, such as school climate, workload, and resource availability, may play a more significant role in determining teacher stress levels related to the environment. Future research could explore

these factors in more detail to develop strategies for improving PE teachers' physical and psychological work environment.

Table 10

Differences in the Level of Coping Strategies of PE Teachers in the Area of Appraisal-focused Strategies When Grouped and Compared According to Variables

Variables	Categories	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U - test	Sig. Level	p-value	Interpretation
Age	Younger	63	59.33	1721.5		0.392	Not Significant
	Older	60	64.81				
Civil Status	Single	38	58.46	1480.5		0.460	Not Significant
	Married	85	63.58				
Length of Service	Shorter	65	60.34	1777.0	0.05	0.583	Not Significant
	Longer	58	63.86				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	88	58.77	1255.5		0.109	Not Significant
	Higher	35	70.13				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	60	64.98	1711.0		0.363	Not Significant
	Higher	63	59.16				

Table 10 reveals the difference in the level of coping strategies of PE teachers in the area of appraisal-focused strategies when grouped and compared according to variables. In terms of age, the computed U was 1721.5 with a p-value of 0.392, which is greater than 0.05 level of significance, interpreted as "not significant." Consequently, the hypothesis, which states "there is no significant difference on the level of coping strategies of PE teachers in the area of appraisal-focused strategies when grouped and compared according to age, was accepted. On the other hand, when grouped and compared according to civil status, there exists no significant difference in the level of coping strategies of PE teachers in the area of appraisal-focused strategies with the computed U of 1480.5 and the p-value of 0.460, which is greater than 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the hypothesis, which states "there is no significant difference in the level of coping strategies of PE teachers in the area of appraisal-focused strategies according to civil status, was accepted. Further analysis of the data shows that when grouped and compared according to length of service, the computed U test was 1777.0 with a p-value of 0.583 which is greater than 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the hypothesis, which states "there is no significant difference in the level of coping strategies of PE teachers in the area of appraisal-focused strategies when grouped and compared according to length of service, was accepted. Furthermore, in terms of highest educational attainment, the result shows that there exists no significant difference with the computed U test of 1255.5 and p-value of 0.109, which is greater than the level of significance of 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis, which states "there is no significant difference on the level of coping strategies of PE teachers in the area of appraisal-focused strategies when grouped and compared according to highest educational attainment, was accepted. Moreover, in terms of average family monthly income, the result shows that there exists no significant difference between the computed U test of 1711.0 and the p-value of 0.363, which is greater than the level of significance of 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis, which states, "there is no significant difference in the level of coping strategies of PE teachers in the area of appraisal-focused strategies when grouped and compared according to average family monthly income, was accepted.

The analysis shows that there are no significant differences in the coping strategies of PE teachers in the area of appraisal-focused strategies when these are compared according to age, civil status, length of service, highest educational attainment, and average family monthly income. This consistency across various demographic and professional factors suggests that PE teachers employ similar appraisal-focused coping strategies irrespective of their personal or professional backgrounds. The hypotheses, which posited that these variables do not significantly affect the coping strategies of PE teachers, are therefore accepted. Moreover, this finding implies that interventions aimed at improving appraisal-focused coping strategies among PE teachers might be universally applicable without the need to tailor them based on age, civil status, length of service, educational attainment, or family income. This could simplify the design and implementation of professional development programs, ensuring that they are inclusive and accessible to all teachers, thereby potentially enhancing the overall effectiveness of such interventions.

In their published article, Pagulong et al. (2022) examine the stress levels and coping mechanisms of physical education teachers. The study reveals significant associations between perceived stress and various coping strategies, including confronting coping, escape avoidance, and positive reappraisal. Similarly, Emeljanovas et al. (2023) explore the connection between teachers' emotional health and their stress-coping methods. Their research highlights those effective coping strategies—such as problem-solving, exercise, and engaging in hobbies—contribute to improved emotional well-being.

Table 11

Differences in the Level of Coping Strategies of PE Teachers in the Area of Problem-focused Strategies When Grouped and Compared According to Variables

Variables	Categories	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U - test	Sig. Level	p-value	Interpretation
Age	Younger	63	58.60	1676.0		0.274	Not Significant
	Older	60	65.58				
Civil Status	Single	38	63.64	1552.0		0.730	Not Significant
	Married	85	61.26				
Length of Service	Shorter	65	60.72	1802.0	0.05	0.671	Not Significant
	Longer	58	63.43				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	88	63.08	1445.0		0.835	Not Significant
	Higher	35	59.29				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	60	67.28	1573.0		0.106	Not Significant
	Higher	63	56.97				

Table 11 illustrates the difference in the level of coping strategies of PE teachers in the area of problem-focused strategies when grouped and compared according to variables. In terms of age, the computed U was 1676.0 with a p-value of 0.274, which is greater than 0.05 level of significance, interpreted as "not significant." Consequently, the hypothesis, which states "there is no significant difference on the level of coping strategies of PE teachers in the area of problem-focused strategies when grouped and compared according to age, was accepted. On the other hand, when grouped and compared according to civil status, there exists no significant difference in PE teachers' coping strategies in the area of problem-focused strategies with the computed U of 1552.0 and the p-value of 0.730, which is greater than 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the hypothesis, which states "there is no significant difference in the level of coping strategies of PE teachers in the area of problem-focused strategies according to civil status, was accepted. Further analysis of the data shows that when grouped and compared according to length of service, the computed U test was 1802.0 with a p-value of 0.671, which is greater than 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the hypothesis, which states "there is no significant difference in the level of coping strategies of PE teachers in the area of problem-focused strategies when grouped and compared according to length of service, was accepted. Furthermore, in terms of highest educational attainment, the result shows that there exists no significant difference with the computed U test of 1445.0 and p-value of 0.835, which is greater than the level of significance of 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis, which states "there is no significant difference on the level of coping strategies of PE teachers in the area of problem-focused strategies when grouped and compared according to highest educational attainment, was accepted. Moreover, in terms of average family monthly income, the result shows that there exists no significant difference between the computed U test of 1573.0 and the p-value of 0.106, which is greater than the level of significance of 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis, which states "there is no significant difference in the level of coping strategies of PE teachers in the area of problem-focused strategies when grouped and compared according to average family monthly income, was accepted.

Relatively, the findings elucidate the discrepancies in coping strategies among PE teachers, especially in problem-focused strategies, when categorized and contrasted based on diverse variables. Regarding age, the computed value indicated no significant difference, leading to the acceptance of the hypothesis that suggests no variance in coping strategies based on age. Similarly, when segmented by civil status, the analysis showed no substantial deviation in coping strategies, resulting in the hypothesis being upheld. Moreover, further examination reveals that the length of service does not impact the coping strategies significantly, thus confirming the hypothesis of no difference based on this variable. Likewise, the highest educational attainment exhibited no significant disparity in coping strategies, supporting the null hypothesis. Finally, considering the average family's monthly income, the findings illustrated no notable variation, leading to the acceptance of the hypothesis indicating no significant difference in coping strategies based on this financial variable.

Pagulong et al. (2022) conducted a study investigating physical education teachers' stress levels and coping mechanisms. The findings reveal that coping mechanisms such as confronting coping, escape avoidance, and positive reappraisal are significantly linked to their perceived stress. Similarly, Quansah et al. (2022), in their research published in BMC Psychology, evaluate the psychometric properties of a coping inventory for stressful situations experienced by physical education teachers. Their study utilizes a multidimensional item response theory analysis to confirm the inventory's effectiveness in measuring coping strategies among these educators.

Table 12

Differences in the Level of Coping Strategies of PE Teachers in the Area of Emotional-focused Strategies When Grouped and Compared According to Variables

Variables	Categories	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U - test	Sig. Level	p-value	Interpretation
Age	Younger	63	58.58	1674.5		0.273	Not Significant
	Older	60	65.59				
Civil Status	Single	38	61.74	1605.0		0.956	Not Significant
	Married	85	62.12				
Length of Service	Shorter	65	58.91	1684.0	0.05	0.306	Not Significant
	Longer	58	65.47				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	88	62.42	1503.0		0.835	Not Significant
	Higher	35	60.94				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	60	66.48	1621.0		0.171	Not Significant
	Higher	63	57.73				

Table 12 shows the difference in the level of coping strategies of PE teachers in the area of emotional-focused strategies when grouped and compared according to variables. In terms of age, the computed U was 1674.5 with a p-value of 0.273, which is greater than 0.05 level of significance, interpreted as "not significant." Consequently, the hypothesis, which states "there is no significant difference on the level of coping strategies of PE teachers in the area of emotional-focused strategies when grouped and compared according to age, was accepted. On the other hand, when grouped and compared according to civil status, there exists no significant difference in PE teachers' coping strategies in the area of emotional-focused strategies with the computed U of 1605.0 and the p-value of 0.956, which is greater than 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the hypothesis which states, "there is no significant difference on the level of coping strategies of PE teachers in the area of emotional-focused strategies according to civil status, was accepted. Further analysis of the data shows that when grouped and compared according to length of service, the computed U test was 1684.0 with a p-value of 0.306, which is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the hypothesis, which states, "there is no significant difference on the level of coping strategies of PE teachers in the area of emotional-focused strategies when grouped and compared according to length of service, was accepted. Furthermore, in terms of highest educational attainment, the result shows that there exists no significant difference with the computed U test of 1503.0 and p-value of 0.835, which is greater than the level of significance of 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis, which states "there is no significant difference on the level of coping strategies of PE teachers in the area of emotional-focused strategies when grouped and compared according to highest educational attainment, was accepted. Moreover, in terms of average family monthly income, the result shows that there exists no significant difference with the computed U test of 1621.0 and p-value of 0.171, which is greater than the level of significance of 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis, "there is no significant difference in the level of coping strategies of PE teachers in the area of emotional-focused strategies when grouped and compared according to average family monthly income, was accepted.

The data revealed the discrepancies in coping strategies among PE teachers, particularly in emotional-focused strategies, when categorized and juxtaposed based on various variables. With respect to age, the computed value indicates no significant difference, affirming the hypothesis that there is no variance in coping strategies by age. Similarly, when grouped by civil status, the analysis shows no substantial deviation in coping strategies, thereby upholding the hypothesis. Further scrutiny reveals that the length of service does not significantly influence coping strategies, thus confirming the hypothesis of no difference based on this variable. Additionally, the highest educational attainment displays no significant disparity in coping strategies, supporting the null hypothesis. Finally, when considering the average family's monthly income, the findings demonstrate no notable variation, leading to the acceptance of the hypothesis that there is no significant difference in coping strategies based on this financial variable.

Schäfer et al. (2019) conducted a study on perceived stress and coping strategies among physical education (PE) teachers, PE pre-service teachers, and PE students, revealing that evasive coping is positively correlated with perceived stress, particularly among PE pre-service teachers. Similarly, Rabago-Mingoa (2017) investigated the stress levels and coping strategies of Filipino teachers in the De La Salle University Research Congress Proceedings.

Table 13
Differences in the Level of Work Performance of PE Teachers When Grouped and Compared According to Variables

Variables	Categories	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U - test	Sig. Level	p-value	Interpretation
Age	Younger	63	54.43	1413.0		0.015	Significant
	Older	60	69.95				
Civil Status	Single	38	55.17	1355.5	0.05	0.154	Not Significant
	Married	85	65.05				
Length of Service	Shorter	65	56.24	1510.5		0.057	Not Significant
	Longer	58	68.46				

Highest Educational Attainment	Lower Higher	88 35	61.96 62.10	1536.5	0.984	Not Significant
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower Higher	60 63	56.63 67.11	1568.0	0.102	Not Significant

Results in Table 13 reflect the difference in the level of work performance of PE teachers when grouped and compared according to variables. Specifically, in the variable age, when the data of the younger and the older groups are compared and tested, the computed U test was 1413.0 with a p-value of 0.015, which is less than the 0.05 level of significance. This indicates that there exists a significant difference in the level of work performance of PE teachers when grouped and compared according to age. Hence, the null hypothesis, which states "there is no significant difference in the level of work performance of PE teachers when grouped and compared according to age," was not accepted. On the other hand, in terms of civil status, the computed U was 1355.5 with a p-value of 0.154, which is greater than the 0.05 level of significance and is interpreted as "not significant." Therefore, the hypothesis, which states, "there is no significant difference in the level of work performance of PE teachers when grouped and compared according to civil status," was accepted. When grouped and compared according to length of service, there exists no significant difference in the level of work performance of PE teachers with the computed U of 1510.5 and p-value of 0.057, which is greater than the level of significance of 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis, which states "there is no significant difference in the level of work performance of PE teachers when grouped and compared according to length of service," was accepted. Moreover, there exists no significant difference in the level of work performance of PE teachers when grouped and compared according to highest educational attainment with the computed U of 1536.5 and p-value of 0.984, which is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Consequently, the hypothesis, which states, "there is no significant difference in the level of work performance of PE teachers when grouped and compared according to highest educational attainment," was accepted. Lastly, in terms of average family monthly income, the result shows that there exists no significant difference with the computed U test of 1568.0 and p-value of 0.102, which is greater than the level of significance of 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis, which states "there is no significant difference in the level of work performance of PE teachers when grouped and compared according to average family monthly income, was accepted.

The data revealed the disparities in work performance among PE teachers when segmented and juxtaposed according to various variables. Regarding age, the data reveals a significant difference, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis that postulated no variance in work performance based on age. Contrarily, when categorized by civil status, the computed values suggest no substantial difference in work performance, thus affirming the hypothesis. Moreover, an in-depth examination demonstrates that length of service does not significantly influence work performance, supporting the hypothesis of no difference based on this factor. Similarly, the highest educational attainment exhibited no significant disparity in work performance, thereby corroborating the null hypothesis. Finally, concerning average family monthly income, the findings indicate no notable variation, leading to the acceptance of the hypothesis positing no significant difference in work performance based on this financial variable.

Cabugatan & Belleza (2024) conducted a study that investigates the influence of work-related stressors and efficacy on the work performance of PE teachers, uncovering significant relationships between these factors and work performance. Similarly, Yan et al. (2022) carried out a systematic review to explore the relationship between competency, job satisfaction, and work performance among university-level PE teachers, highlighting the positive impact of competency and job satisfaction on their work performance.

Table 14
Significant Relationship between the Level of Stress and the Level of Coping Strategies

Variables	N	rho	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Level of Stress	123	0.215	0.017	0.05	Significant
Level of Coping Strategies	123				

As shown in the table, a significant relationship existed between the level of stress and the level of coping strategies, as supported by the computed rho of 0.215 with a p-value of 0.017. Hence, the hypothesis, which states, "there is no significant relationship between the level of stress and the level of coping strategies," was rejected for obtaining a p-value of less than 0.05 level of significance.

The table demonstrates a notable connection between stress levels and coping strategies. Consequently, the hypothesis stating "there is no significant relationship between stress levels and coping strategies" was dismissed due to the significant findings. This suggests that varying stress levels are indeed related to different coping strategies among participants. The results imply that the higher the level of practice, the higher the level of competence. On the other hand, a lower level of practice would also mean a low level of competence. Thus, the relationship between these variables is directly proportional.

Ga-as and Luzano (2024) investigated the pervasive issue of stress, examining its impact on well-being and academic performance and identifying effective coping strategies. Likewise, Drüge et al. (2022) compared stress levels and coping strategies, highlighting differences in stress-inducing areas and coping mechanisms.

Conclusions:

As the results reveal, it can be concluded that PE teachers generally experienced low levels of stress except from specific items in environmental and personal factors, which revealed significance. It shows that PE teachers experience high-stress levels due to the limited utilization of break time due to workload, insufficient take-home pay, inadequate PE equipment and facilities, and insufficient budget allocation for PE supplies, which causes stress and shows that PE teachers experience burnout. Moreover, the majority of PE teachers are younger, have shorter years in public service, and hold bachelor's degrees. Given the demographic profile of younger, less experienced PE teachers, they are likely to experience higher levels of stress due to the demands of the role and the challenges of early career development. PE teachers may face unique stressors related to job expectations, workload, and the pressure to meet performance standards.

However, results indicated that there was no significant difference in coping strategies in terms of appraisal, problem-focused, and emotional focus when grouped and compared to the variables. It concludes that regardless of their demographic characteristics, they employed similar coping strategies, indicating a common approach to managing stress and adversity.

The implications drawn also conclude that the lower the level of stress experienced and the greater the level of coping strategies utilized by the PE teachers, the higher the probability of having a high level of work performance. Furthermore, it is concluded, based on the findings, that the main reason that PE teachers have low levels of stress in terms of the stressors discussed was the great level of coping strategies they have evidently utilized. The same belief was held about PE teachers' high level of work performance. The reason for having utilized applicable coping strategies resulted in a low level of stress, and consequently, the PE teachers obtained a very satisfactory performance.

Based on the findings of this study, it concludes that the majority of the PE teachers have limited utilization of break time due to workload, insufficient take-home pay, inadequate PE equipment and facilities, and insufficient budget allocation for PE supplies. Therefore, prioritization of adequate budget for PE supplies, improvement in the existing PE facilities, and sufficient trainings and development opportunities for PE teachers would prove beneficial for PE teachers.

Acknowledgement

Our deepest gratitude to my esteemed panelists for the invaluable guidance they provided me through this project. Our thanks to my colleagues who were supportive until we reached our destination. Lastly, to our family, who believed in us to finish this project, whose faith and love kept us soldiering on, our deepest gratitude.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare the absence of any conflict of interest that could have influenced the content or conclusions of this paper. They affirm that no financial, personal, or professional relationship influenced them in this project.

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